

Internal Conflicts of Teacher Educational Institutions and NEP 2020: A Systematic Review Study

Paper Id : 19211 Submission Date : 2024-08-13 Acceptance Date : 2024-08-22 Publication Date : 2024-08-25
This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.13733966

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/remarking.php#8>

Monali Debnath

Research Scholar
Education
Assam University
Silchar, Assam

Abstract

Teachers play a vital role in ensuring learners internalize the educational aim. A good teacher is seen as a master constructor who moulds their students' futures. However, there are still a lot of common causes for the decline in teacher preparation. Thus, the study is designed to identify the internal conflicts faced by the teachers in teacher education within the Teacher Educational Institutions (TEIs). The methodology of the study is based on 30 document analysis of secondary data collected from varied publications, research papers, journals, and reports. The study examined the internal disputes that occur in Teacher Educational Institutions (TEIs) and offered solutions to address the issues from the perspective of NEP, 2020.

Keywords Teacher education, Internal conflicts, Teacher Educational Institutions (TEIs), NEP 2020.

Introduction

Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs) have seen numerous changes and transitions throughout the years regarding their curriculum, methodology, and procedure for delivering teacher education. Currently, 24199 courses are offered by the 16917 Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs) that make up India (NCTE, 2001). According to the information, there are 935 universities in total and 16917 Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs). Deduction of 935 universities, there are roughly 15,982 stand-alone TEIs present in India. However, as per the Higher Education Statistics Report 2022, there are 45,473 colleges are presently active in India, which the government planned to upgrade into integrated colleges as B.A /B.Sc. and B.Com will be merged with B.Ed. degrees on the guidelines of NEP, 2020 (Misra, 2020). These integrations led to the necessity of rearranging the curriculum for teacher education where the Department of Education's roles and responsibilities will increase, and they will be viewed as essential to strengthening the teachers' existing position.

Objective of study

1. To explore the internal conflicts of teacher educational institutes through recent articles, reports, and NEP 2020.
2. To provide a resolution from NEP 2020 for the improvement of the present conditions of teacher education.

Review of Literature

The definition of a teacher, the nature of education, the teaching-learning process, and teaching strategies have changed over the past few decades. These changes may be attributable to societal practices such as stratification, mobility, development, modernization, westernization, privatization, and globalization (Samadhiya, 2023). The changes that took place over the period in the form of transition into the conduct and living of the people of India and the world (Miah & Debnath, 2022). In the realm of the present scenario, the role of education during these days has changed the cause of many prevalent factors and acting as agents at social, psychological, and philosophical levels (Chowdhury, 2021). Therefore, the education of teachers needs to be based on present conditions as leaders are required to be competent enough to adjust to this fast-changing society, which is quick into adapting the transition where, teachers as a leader required to be well enough to adapt to the change, and simultaneously work accordingly to shape their students, classroom learning experience, school environment, proper evaluation, examination, accurate management, and administration (Smith, 2021). The change and challenges in the educational field for students as well as teachers require a need to suggest and bring new elements, to eradicate several outgrowing issues at

social, psychological, and philosophical levels (Anwar, 2017). These outgrowing issues in the educational field can be thrown out of the system with proper educators, and directors in the form of teachers (Mayer & Oancea, 2021). It is believed that teachers are best to bring any revolution as they are true leaders.

The changing role of Teachers with the evolution of Teacher's Training and Education:

Teachers from the ancient period have undergone various roles from being the 'Guru', 'God', 'Acharya', and 'Pandits, within the context of defining the meaning of teachers as ultimate superior recalled in the ancient mantras i.e. "Guru Brahma, Guru Vishnu, Guru Devo Maheshwara, Guru Sakshat Parabrahma, Tasmai Shri Guruve Namah". However, the role and meaning of teachers transited from period to period as looked upon during the period of the Muslim era when teachers were 'maulvi' considered as 'Spiritual preachers at mosque' and acquired the highest respect (Bhatia, Chadha, Kadyan, & Sharma, 1988). With colonization, Modern Education came where different forms of education engrossed with Christian missionaries to spread Christianity and modern outlook into imparting education then spiritualism, self-realization, and salvation. The modern system of education brought the concept of involving teachers of Indian origin with a British outlook which included the provision for providing training to teachers (Borah, 2012). The term training was first introduced by the dept. of Training in 1971 for the development of a teacher's attitude, skills, and behavioural patterns in a systematic manner (Sexena, Mishra, & Mohenty, 2014). However, Wood Despatch (1954) suggested improvement of teacher's education, the Indian education commission (1882) also suggested examination for principles and practice teaching, a shorter course of training for permanent employment into secondary and graduate level, Hartog Committee (1929) suggested for in-service education of teacher and refresher course for school teacher, University education commission (1949) suggested refresher course for High school and Inter college teachers, Education commission (1964) suggested correspondence institute, summer institutes, refresher cantered, in-service program, conference, seminar, symposium, NPE (1986) recommended that major institute as UGC, NCERT etc must strengthen the national system of education to cope with the emerging need of the nation and POA (1992) (Bhatia, Chadha, Kadyan, & Sharma, 1988). Teacher education came with a means to develop the qualitative aspect of teachers so that they can provide a better learning atmosphere. Thus, Teacher Education is a program that is designed for teacher trainees to get them equipped with the right form of teaching technique, skills, attitudes, behaviour, and approaches towards teaching, also carrying a proper teaching-learning process (Sexena, Mishra, & Mohenty, 2014).

Methodology

The nature of the study is descriptive and based on the document analysis collected through secondary data from articles, reports, and previous research papers.

Research Design: The study is descriptive based on document analysis collected from varied available resources from related journals, articles, reports, and NEP 2020 policy reports.

Analysis

The study is based on 30 document analyses of previous articles, journals, books, and reports to understand the existing inner conflicts between the institution and the teachers in the development of teacher education. Also, based upon the conflicts discussed the NEP 2020 as viewed to resolve and address many of the prevalent problems for bringing change in the system.

Internal Conflicts recognized in Teacher Education from NEP 1986-till today:

The enhancement of teachers' positions has long been a concern and a key topic about teacher education. During the development process, a variety of hurdles were noted, including problems with teaching methods and learning practices from antiquity to the Middle Ages, when teachers were regarded as "gurus," "maulvis," and "gods." But as education developed, ideas like globalization, privatization, westernization, and modernization surfaced, changing the role of teachers accordingly (Bhatia, Chadha, Kadyan, & Sharma, 1988). However, as societal dynamics change, there is an increasing need for more qualified educators who can utilize technology effectively. As a result, the field of preparation for encouraging teacher education has arisen as a relative means of overcoming the obstacles that face teacher education before it even begins.

Furthermore, because of these societal dynamics and earlier research investigations, an array of issues was identified as contributing to the escalating internal conflicts in teacher education across different government and private institutions, colleges, and universities. A few noticeable internal conflicts that are considered as major into

deteriorating teacher education includes, the *absence of adequate infrastructure* is a problem that stems from a lack of fundamental resources for delivering teacher education to ensure maximum involvement (Richard, 2016), the *increased number of untrained teachers* that growing inexperienced teaching practices with prevalent reasons as a larger number of participants at in-service and pre-service training centres (Dwivedi, 2012), the *outmoded curriculum* that fails to serve the purpose of meeting the learning goals, the absence of periodic reviews, the erroneous revision of critical analysis, and the tardiness of updates (Mahapatra, 2022), the *problem of isolation* that is fragmented from the mainstream of higher education at the university, college, and school levels (Jamwal, 2012), the *insufficient Funding* at the state and district level for educational institutions such as SCERT, DIETS, and CTEs which has an impact on the organization and flow of resources needed to deliver educational programs, the inappropriate *teacher-pupil ratio* with a growing number of students jammed into one teacher's small classroom makes it difficult to provide optimal learning experiences (Mahapatra, 2022), *lacking in providing proper internships*- due to the short period the goal of allowing students to practice teaching in classrooms for at least six weeks is not practiced (Sumathi & Kothandaraman, 2016), and *lacks at addressing the increase in social issues* such as growing population explosion, unemployment, illiteracy, poverty, social disparity, etc wherein, the simultaneous problem at the societal level acts as an active agent in the form of social issues affecting the teacher education system (Dahiya & Dr. Sarita, 2016).

Quality Development Conflicts of Teacher Education:

Teacher education is crucial for both professional growth and interpersonal kindness. Every industry has expectations and goals that must be met to be successful. However, the following are the main obstacles recognized from the previous studies in reaching the intended result as observed include; a *lack of appropriate in-service training* that showed a lack of comprehension of certain qualitative abilities and procedures that were required to be learned and practiced in teaching-learning settings at B.Ed., M.Ed., Del.Ed., and other levels (Mishra, 2020), then the *inability to accommodate technical skills* which provide less scope to adapt the technological information that is necessary for future assistance as the use of a computer, projector, digital board, etc (Dwivedi, 2012), then, *practicing improper instructional methods in educational settings*, which results in a lack of ability to comprehend real-life events and provide impromptu educational experiences (Akhter & Mir, 2018), *lacking at bringing quality research and teacher training programmes*, research and development will be carried out frequently and that will increase the sound education system (Dahiya & Dr. Sarita, 2016), and *privatization vs. government*, the growing privatization among institutional setup, and the continuous clash between private and government organisations brought the issue of unethical practices into the educational system.

Major Internal Conflicts of Teacher Education from the Perspective of NEP, 2020:

Dysfunctional Teacher Education Institutions- According to the NEP, 2020, many teacher education institutes were engaging in improper labour practices and had fictitious accreditation. These rituals are extremely common and are carried out throughout India. The Justice J. S. Verma Commission (2012) reported that 10,000 TEI were practicing for fraudulent degrees at great financial risk (MHRD, 2020).

Poor quality content and pedagogy practices- The absence of practical exposure resulting from a variety of factors, such as a lack of resources, time limits, opportunities, etc., is one of the low-quality content and pedagogy practices.

Inactive Administrative networking- The lack of active administrative networking among the many institutions of learning regulated the gaps between various sectors, deteriorated collaboration, increased distribution, and did not provide community service to improve teachers' participation as role models.

Unstructured and Lack of Uniformity in Institutional Standards- The standards and reputation of teacher education institutions are consistently undermined by the disorganized and non-uniform nature of the diverse educational system (Aithal & Aithal, 2020). It is discovered to be a major factor in progress delays and a lack of room for advancement. NEP, 2020 is worried about sustainable development to offer high-quality teacher preparation, nonetheless.

Degraded research work- The research's current purpose is to compile a list of publications rather than to identify or contribute to social problems, because of the growing number of educational institutions (Sharma & Kumar, 2022). The potential for enhancement is based on in-depth study in a certain area. When it came to teaching techniques, this component was discovered to be missing.

Language Barrier- The absence of multi-linguistics competency in performing multiple roles as teacher, guide, philosopher, creator, role model, and counselor has created a multilinguistic approach (Dar & Jan, 2023). Therefore, this barrier creates a communication gap between the learner and the teacher educators.

Lack of Autonomy to Teachers- The institutional internal processes were unable to undergo necessary reform, decision-making, or suitable transformation due to a variety of reasons involving a lack of autonomy (Soni, 2022). The effectiveness of teachers and their methods of instruction have a significant impact on students' academic performance.

Deployment of teachers in rural and disadvantaged areas- Teachers are deployed when they are positioned appropriately to handle a particular issue or to provide additional support in the field of education. Due to many social and geographic restrictions in the form of personal amenities, it is difficult in rural and underprivileged areas.

Degradation of teacher's identity and role- The main challenge is to revive the image of teachers that is continuously degrading due to the various prevalent factors present in the existing system of education. Society and community are also a factor behind the derogative image of teachers along with functional.

Result and Discussion

The Suggestion of NEP, 2020 to Overcome the Teacher Education Challenges:

Inclusion of Integrated educational program into existing curriculum: the introduction of a newly updated curriculum in the shape of the ITEP (Integrated Teacher Education Program), which is intended specifically to offer integrated courses leading to bachelor's degrees, as, B.A + B.Ed. or B.Sc. + B.Ed.(4years), and M. A+ M.Ed. or M.Sc. + M.Ed.(3years)

Inclusion of teachers into enculturation towards empowerment: The NEP 2020; integrating teachers in enculturation through school engagement; creating educational objectives; refining policy suggestions and creating excellent pedagogy with the help of a variety of faculty development programs (Giri, Parida, Nayak, & Dash, 2024). This inclusion will also help to contribute through research endeavours.

Introducing National Professional and Career Development: The goal of the NEP 2020 is to achieve the predefined purpose of professional development, career growth management, teaching strengthening, and teacher preparation. As a result, a Continuous Professional Development (CPD) unit is established for teachers' professional development throughout the entire educational process as; at the *foundational stage* it induces the play-way method, language proficiency, etc., and at the *preparatory stage* it introduces an interactive classroom learning for which teachers will be trained into co-curricular and curricular activities with various cultural programs, workshops, competitions, sports activity, etc, whereas, at the *middle stage*, it includes subject matter experts who possess the necessary subject knowledge to foster students' curiosity, and at *high school stage* concepts of the multidisciplinary, concept of flexibility, holistic development, creativity and innovation will be explored (MHRD, 2020).

Conducting a frequent survey to study the effect of the study: The NEP 2020, suggested a measure to improve the quality of teacher education institutions through a frequent survey at the educational institutions to be conducted by NAAC, NCERT, and NCTE.

Autonomy to curriculum modification and teachers: The institutions and faculty will be provided with the authority and autonomy to innovate the curriculum for the development of learners (Bera & Pramanik, 2023). It will include the reduction of curriculum content, learning process, and flexibility in real-life application.

Conversion of stand-alone colleges into multidisciplinary colleges: The stand-alone colleges will be converted to multidisciplinary colleges for the inclusion of high quality, flexibility, and extension of opportunities to be ample in numbers (Acharya, 2024). This will extend the reach of one discipline competency to be merged with the other discipline to address the problem of any related concept.

Developed pedagogical framework for teachers' qualitative improvement: Under the NCERT pedagogical framework the ECCE will be improved among the Anganwadi's co-workers/teachers under the mentorship of cluster resources centres (MHRD, 2020). It will provide 10+2 educated personnel, a degree into ECCE of 6 months only, and less qualified one of 1-year diploma.

Development of Indian traditional knowledge- It made a provision to develop the use of the Sanskrit language along with knowledge of the traditional language and proficiency in the local language to improve the skill of communication and teaching process.

Digitalization- Incorporating assistive technology, augmented reality, virtual reality, eBooks, PDFs, and other digital learning resources into a course can speed up the teaching-learning process (Muralidharan, Shanmugan, & Klochkov, 2022). This can be used as an asset for teacher education programs, where teachers will be trained to use digital equipment among the learners.

Vocational Skill Development- In all educational institutions, the policy centered on advancing vocational education beginning in the sixth grade, with the requirement that 50% of higher-level students be familiar with skills-based learning (Babu, 2023). As part of quality improvement, this skill-based education will help instructors acquire the necessary vocational abilities through appropriate teacher preparation.

Conclusion

The NEP, 2020 was implemented to improve the quality of teacher education for those who lack the necessary skills to use numerous elements properly and practically in schools, colleges, and universities (Mondol, 2024). Years of surveys, dropout rates, illiteracy, and a lack of technological proficiency led to the need to reorganize and present a variety of institutions to collaborate in the areas of improving the quality of teachers, empowering teachers to change society, recognizing teachers as problem solvers with the ability to innovate, and providing teachers with access to participate in curriculum suggestions. Educators should make choices on research, textbooks, extracurricular activities, improved teaching methods, and technology use to enhance the learning process (Bhatia, Dr. Rinkey, & Kaur, 2024). The NEP, 2020 is still grappling with a number of these issues, including numerous social, political, and economic problems that arise in a global context. Nevertheless, regular and ongoing surveys and the preparation of reports based on the data gathered are intended to serve as a means of addressing impending deficiencies around teacher preparation. It is necessary to update the teacher education program's curriculum in accordance with a holistic perspective. It ought to be rebuilt using the abilities of critical thinking development in positive and technologically pedagogical methods. Regretfully, there are still several issues with the system (Miah & Debnath, 2022). It is conceivable for teacher education to have a bright future after conducting a critical analysis and consulting with experts in the area. The NCTE and state governments may make significant contributions to raising the standard of teacher education.

References

1. Acharya, S. (2024). NEP 2020: Challenges in Teacher Education. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Technology*, 10(10), 517-523.
2. Aithal, P., & Aithal, S. (2020). Analysis of the Indian National Education Policy 2020 towards Achieving its Objectives. *International Journal of Management, Technology & Social Sciences*, 5(2), 19-41.
3. Akhter, S., & Mir, T. R. (2018). Issues and Challenges of Teacher Education In India. *International Journal of Yogic, Human Movement & Sports Sciences*, 3(2), 573-576.
4. Anwar, M. E. (2017). Teacher's Education in India: A Critical Review of various Issues and Challenges. *BEST International Journal of Management Information Technology and Engineering*, 5(8), 141-150.
5. Babu, D. R. (2023). NEP 2020: Issues and Challenges ahead in Teacher. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 11(3), 4560-4567. doi:10.25215/1103.424
6. Bera, M., & Pramanik, K. C. (2023). NEP 2020 Study: Challenges, Approaches, Changes, Opportunities, and Criticism. *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 5(5), 1-6. doi:10.36948/ijfmr.2023.v05i05.6902
7. Bhatia, D., Dr. Rinkey, & Kaur, J. (2024). NEP 2020: Transforming the Role of Teacher Educators. *International Journal of All Research Education and Scientific Methods*, 12(1), 269-275.
8. Bhatia, K., Chadha, P., Kadyan, K., & Sharma, S. (1988). *Modern Indian Education And its Problems*. Ludhiana: Tandon Publications.
9. Borah, R. R. (2012). Impact of Politics and Concerns with the Indian Education System. *International Journal of Education Planning and Administration*, 2(2), 91-86.
10. Chowdhury, D. (2021). Teacher Education in 21st Century in the light of Indian Scenario: Deduction for future Proposition. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Educational Research*, 10(2), 132-137.
11. Dahiya, R., & Dr. Sarita. (2016). Recent Issues and Problems in India: Teacher Education. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development*,

- 3(9), 19-22.
12. Dar, D. A., & Jan, T. (2023). Changing Role of Teacher Education in view of NEP 2020. *Journal of Xi'an University of Architecture and Technology*, 15(1), 144-156.
 13. Desai, A. J. (2012). Problem of Teacher Education in India. *International Journal for Research in Education*, 1(1), 54-58.
 14. Doyran, F. (2012). *Research on Teacher Education & Training*. Greece: Athens Institute for Education & Research.
 15. Dwivedi, S. K. (2012). Teacher Education: Issues and Challenges in India. *The Journal of Progressive Education*, 5(2), 17-24.
 16. Giri, S., Parida, S., Nayak, S. L., & Dash, A. (2024). Problems and Issues in Teacher Education in India. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, 12(2), 852-860.
 17. Jamwal, D. S. (2012). Teacher Education: Issues and their Remedies. *Research India Publication*, 2(2), 85-90. Retrieved from <https://www.ripublication.com/ijepa.htm>
 18. Mahapatra, M. (2022). The New Education policy 2020: The Good and The Bad and What is left to be Done. *International Journal for Research Trends and Innovation*, 7(12), 782-786.
 19. Mayer, D., & Oancea, A. (2021). Teacher Education Research Policy and Practice: Finding Future Research Directions. *Oxford Review of Education*, 47(1), 1-7. doi:10.1080/03054985.2021.1853934
 20. MHRD. (2020). *National Education Policy*. Delhi: Government of India.
 21. Miah, A. S., & Debnath, D. (2022). Teacher Education in India: Issues and Concerns. *International Journal of Science and Research*, 11(6), 137-140.
 22. Mishra, P. (2020). Issues and challenges in teacher education. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Education and Research*, 5(5), 42-44.
 23. Misra, P. K. (2020). Transforming Teacher Education in India: Ten New Roles for Departments of Education in Universities. *Shanlax International Journal of Education*, 8(3), 84-88. Retrieved from <http://www.shanlaxjournals.com>
 24. Mondol, P. (2024). Exploring the Role of Teachers as Reflected in NEP 2020. *International Journal of Research and Review*, 11(5), 482-495. doi:10.52403/ijrr.20240556
 25. Muralidharan, K., Shanmugan, K., & Klochkov, Y. (2022). The New Education Policy 2020, Digitalization and Quality of Life in India: Some Refelction. *Education Science*, 12(75), 1-21. doi:10.3390/educsci12020075
 26. NCTE. (2001, September 4). *National Council for Teacher Education*. Retrieved August 18, 2024, from <https://ncte.gov.in/Website/NCTEACT12.aspx>.
 27. Richard, J. A. (2016). Problems of Teacher Education in India. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education*, 2(1), 714-720.
 28. Samadhiya, D. K. (2023). Political Effects and Issues with the Indian Educational System. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, 4(9), 1511-1515.
 29. Sexena, N., Mishra, B., & Mohenty, R. (2014). *Teacher Education*. Meerat: Lall Book Depot.
 30. Sharma, S., & Kumar, T. (2022). Problems and Opportunities in Teacher Education in context of National Educational Policy, 2020. *Journal for Research Trends & Innovation*, 7(7), 1504-1508.
 31. Smith, C. M. (2021). Rethinking Teacher Education: The Trouble with Accountability. *Oxford Review of Education*, 47(1), 8-24. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/03054985.2020>
 32. Soni, R. (2022). Challenges and Issues in National Educational Policy 2020. *International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science*, 4(3), 2026-2031.
 33. Sumathi, & Kothandaraman, D. (2016). Issues and Problems of Teacher Education. *International Journal of Science Technology and Management*, 5(8), 723-727.